

quite consistent with the structure (Id). The main peaks may be assigned as follows : m/e 469(M^+), 438($M^+ - OCH_3$), 410($M^+ - COOCH_3$), 274(III), 234.5 (M^{++}), 233 (IV), 191($410 - CO$) $^{++}$ and 190. The two acylium ion peaks at m/e 274 and 233 confirm the presence of acyclic ketone group.

Similar condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with 7-methoxyisochroman-1, 4-dione⁵ afforded (Ic) which was esterified to give (Ie). The acid (Ic) on degradation with alkaline potassium permanganate furnished α -picolinic acid. It is therefore obvious that this type of condensation is general and results in the formation of compounds of the type (I). The mechanism of the condensation has been described in the previous communication.¹

Experimental

1-(2'-Carboxy-4', 5'-dimethoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ib): A solution of 6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,4-dione (0.12 g.) and 2, 3-dichloronaphthoquinone (0.1 g.) in pyridine (2 ml.) was refluxed for 24 hours. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, residue taken up in water, and the mixture filtered. The dark red crude *pyrrocoline* afforded shining needles (50 mg.) from acetic acid, m. p. 265°. (Found : C, 68.3 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{26}H_{17}O_7N$ requires : C, 68.6; H, 3.7; N, 3.1%). ν_{max} 1702 cm^{-1} (acid carbonyl), 1690 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1675 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

1-(2'-Carbomethoxy-4', 5'-dimethoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Id): The above acid was treated with ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (1 g.) and left overnight. The excess of diazomethane was decomposed by adding a few drops of glacial acetic acid and the ether solution filtered to collect the *ester*. Crystallisation from acetic acid yielded shining red needles (20 mg.), m.p. 238°. (Found : C, 68.9 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 2.8 : $C_{27}H_{19}O_7N$ requires : C, 69.1 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 3.0%) ν_{max} 1722 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl), 1682 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1650 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

Oxidative degradation: The acid (Ib ; 0.1 g.) was refluxed with aqueous potassium permanganate (0.4 g. in 20 ml.) and 10% sodium hydroxide solution (4 ml.) for 6 hrs. and then cooled. Excess of potassium permanganate was destroyed by addition of a few drops of alcohol, the precipitated manganese dioxide filtered off and the colourless filtrate was made strongly alkaline and concentrated. The concentrated solution was made just acidic with concentrated hydrochloric acid, evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, and the

residue extracted with ethyl alcohol (5 ml.). A mixture of this solution (1 ml.), a crystal of cyanogen bromide and a little of β -naphthylamine was warmed gently for some time when an orange colour developed indicating the presence of α -picolinic acid.

1-(2'-Carboxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ic): 7-methoxyisochroman-1, 4-dione (0.1 g.) and 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone (0.1 g.) were taken in pyridine (2 ml.) and the mixture refluxed for 24 hrs. The excess of pyridine was distilled off in vacuum, the deep red residue taken up in water and filtered. The *phthaloyl pyrrocoline* crystallised from acetic acid in bright red prisms (40 mg.), m.p. 263°. (Found : C, 70.2 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{25}H_{15}O_6N$ requires : C, 70.6 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 3.3%).

1-(2'-Carbomethoxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2, 3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ie): The above acid was esterified with diazomethane in the usual manner. Crystallisation from acetic acid afforded bright red needles of the *ester*, m. p. 202°. (Found : C, 71.0 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 3.0 : $C_{26}H_{17}O_6N$ requires : C, 71.1 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 3.2%). ν_{max} 1722 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl), 1695 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1670 cm^{-1} (quinone carbonyl).

Oxidative degradation: The above acid was degraded by aqueous potassium permanganate in presence of 10% sodium hydroxide, worked up in the same way as described in the previous case. The test of α -picolinic acid was done in a similar way.

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Inhibitive Effect of some Compounds Towards Corrosion of Copper in Potassium Persulphate Solution

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TURRENTINE¹ studied the dissolution of copper in an ammonical solution of persulphate. Scagliarini and Torelli² showed that copper acts as a catalytic agent in the oxidation of ammonia by persulphate. Ditz³ observed no formation of activated oxygen or

sulphur dioxide during the action but Levi⁴ et. al found that a gas is slowly evolved and a layer of cupric oxide is formed on the metal. Rabald⁵ concluded that in potassium persulphate solution the dissolution of metal and alloys is to an extent of 72 g/m²/day.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitive action of heterocyclic compounds towards corrosion of copper in 0.1M aqueous solution of potassium persulphate.

Experimental

Copper specimens of size 3×6 cm (26 S.W.G.) were used. Preparation, testing and cleaning procedures for specimen were adopted as those described in previous publication⁶. For the study of corrosion and its inhibition 250 ml of 0.1M potassium persulphate solution was taken for immersion of each specimen. All experiments were carried out in duplicate and mean values are taken into consideration. Experiments were performed at 31°±1° temperature. Potassium persulphate was used of S. Merck quality. The compounds were of A. R. grade. Experimental results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CORROSION INHIBITION FOR COPPER IN 0.1M POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE SOLUTION

Size of specimen : 3 × 6 cm, duration:30 minutes. temp.,31°

Concentration of inhibitor	Loss mg	Loss ₂ mg/dm	Inhibition %
0.0	245	680	—
<i>Pyridine</i>			
0.004	26.4	73.3	89
0.008	20.0	55.5	92
0.012	15.3	42.5	94
0.02	10.1	28.0	96
0.04	10.0	27.8	96
<i>Phenazine</i>			
0.004	28.2	78.3	89
0.008	17.5	48.6	93
0.012	10.0	27.8	96
0.02	3.0	8.33	99
0.04	1.00	2.78	100
<i>Acridine</i>			
0.004	48.0	133	80
0.008	29.0	80.5	87
0.012	12.0	33.3	94
0.02	7.0	19.4	96
0.04	4.0	11.1	98
<i>Xanthine</i>			
0.004	27.0	75.0	88
0.008	21.0	58.3	90
0.012	19.0	52.8	91
0.02	16.0	44.4	92
0.04	15.3	42.5	94

For the galvanostatic studies the copper specimen used had an effective area of 4 sq. cm. The experimental procedure adopted was as given by Gatos⁷. From the weight loss method Phenazine is found to be an excellent inhibitor, hence polarization study was carried out only in the case of Phenazine. The polarization results are represented in Fig. 1,

Fig. 1. Influence of current densities on anode and cathode potentials.

- (A) 0.1M K₂S₂O₈ (un inhibited)
- (B) 0.1M K₂S₂O₈ + 0.04% phenazine

Results :

In the case of pyridine 89 to 96% protection was noted between the concentration range from 0.004 to 0.04%. Its inhibitive power increases with increase in concentration of the substance. Phenazine and acridine afforded nearly 100% and 98% protection respectively at their highest concentration. Xanthine is found comparatively less effective in inhibitive power than pyridine, acridine and phenazine. Its inhibitive power increases with increase in concentration of inhibitor. It afforded 94% protection at its highest concentration.

In general, we can arrange the inhibitive power in the order : Xanthine < Pyridine < Acridine < Phenazine.

All the compounds can be considered as good corrosion inhibitors for copper in 0.1 M potassium persulphate solution., when inhibitors employed brown coloured film on the metal surface was observed in all the cases. The film was not easily soluble in 5% sulphuric acid solution.

When external current is applied cathode gets more polarized in comparison with anode. Similar behaviour was observed in the case of phenazine but magnitude of cathodic polarization is much more than that of anode. Hence the reaction is under cathodic control.

The possibility of correlating structural characteristics with the inhibitor properties of organic substances is justified by the fact that the metal, inhibitor interactions are based on chemisorption. The electron density of the organic polar group that can be defined as the reaction centre for the establishment of adsorption is obviously important, since it is possible to assume a bond of lewis acid-base type, generally with the inhibitor as the electron donor and the metal as the electron acceptor. The strength of this bond depends on the characteristics of both the adsorbent and

adsorbate. Most of the organic inhibitors are compounds with at least one polar functional groups having atoms of oxygen, sulphur, selenium and nitrogen.

In the present work pyridine derivatives have been studied. They have nitrogen as an electron donor atom. Hence nitrogen is regarded as the reactions centre for the establishment of the chemisorption process.

When copper plates is immersed in aqueous solution of potassium persulphate it gives Cu^{+2} ions according to the following reactions.

Acridine derivatives are widely used as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium and iron (II) in acidic media. Acridine and phenazine are found as excellent corrosion inhibitors for copper in 0.1M potassium persulphate solution. According to Kuznetsov^{1,2} and Iofa^{1,3} ions of nitrogen containing inhibitors are capable of being adsorbed predominantly on the most active regions of the dissolving metal. They reported that inhibition obtained by acridine is due to formation of protective layer on the metal surface.

It is qualitatively observed that these compounds give different types of coloured precipitates with copper ions in potassium persulphate solution.

Compounds	Colour of ppt,
Pyridine	Bright blue
Phenazine	Yellowish green crystalline
Acridine	Orange coloured crystalline
Xanthine	Slight white precipitate.

This is a strong evidence that most of the compounds have tendency to form complex compounds with copper ions. Due to the formation of insoluble complex compound, a thin adherent film is formed on the metal surface which prevents corrosion.

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Optically Active Unsymmetrical Ketones from S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-Bromobutane

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OPTICALLY active unsymmetrical aliphatic ketones¹ of the type, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}$ have been prepared by the Grignard reaction using optically active S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane and different alkyl cyanides. Treatment of 86% optically pure S-(+)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (I), $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$ dm), with bromine and red phosphorus resulted in S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (II), $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$ dm), which gave Grignard reagent (III). It was then reacted with different alkyl cyanides to obtain desired optically active ketones (IV). The alkyl cyanides are prepared from their respective alkyl bromides, while methyl, ethyl and *n*-propyl cyanides as they are water soluble were prepared from acetamide, propionamide and *n*-butyramide, respectively^{2,3}.

The bromine atom is away from the active center and not attached directly to the asymmetric carbon atom, therefore it is not disturbed during the reaction, hence the different alkyl substituted ketones were found to be optically active. The maximum rotation found in case of S-(+)-3-methyl-5-decanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 3.04$ ($l=1$ dm) and minimum rotation in case of S-(+)-3-methyl-5-tridecanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 0.32$ ($l=1$ dm).

The physical properties including optical activity and infrared spectra are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol^{4,5}: The fusel oil contains one of the constituents as optically active S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol which was obtained by fractional distillation through 16 inch long column, b. p. $126^\circ - 128^\circ$. $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$ dm); $d_4^{25} 0.8279$; $n_D^{25} 1.450$.

*S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane*⁶: It was prepared by bromination of S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (320 g.) with red phosphorus (20.7 g.) and liquid bromine (266.6 g., 86.1 ml.). The resulting S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane was obtained at $116^\circ - 118^\circ$. Yield 57.3%. $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$ dm); $d_4^{25} 1.255$; $n_D^{25} 1.455$.

General method for the preparation of S-(+)-2-methyl-1-butyl n-alkyl ketone: To the Grignard reagent prepared from S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (0.2 ml), dry magnesium (0.2 mole) and ether (100 ml), the alkyl cyanide (0.2 mole) in ether (40 ml) was added dropwise during 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1 hr and kept overnight. On the next day the Grignard complex was decomposed by ammonium chloride solution (10%, 500 ml). The ketone was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled under reduced pressure.